

DEVELOPING COMPETENCIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: In this thesis, the reforms being carried out today in preschool educational organizations, the development of competencies in the development of children in the state curriculum for the first step, the development of cognitive abilities in preschool children, the implementation of STEAM technologies in play centers.

Keywords: Preschool education, preschool children, competence, cognition, STEAM technology, First Step State Curriculum.

On December 29, 2016, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev adopted a resolution "On measures to further improve the preschool education system for 2017-2021." In fact, the modern world is rapidly developing. Classes are being held not only in the economy, but also in education, using new modern technologies and new methods. Classes in preschool educational organizations are held in 5 centers: language and speech, construction and mathematics, science and nature center, art, role-playing and dramatization centers. In these centers, activities are carried out using modern technologies. One of them is STEAM technology, in each center children are trained individually.

STEAM is the English word for Science (science), Technology (technology), Engineering (engineering), Arts (art), and Mathematics (mathematics). Using these technologies, a child develops cognitive abilities, knowledge, skills, and competencies. What is competence? What role does it play in a child's development?

Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, abilities and values of a child. The competency approach to education of preschool children includes the formation of children's ability to effectively respond to cognitive needs, problems and opportunities, the development of moral norms and values, communication with other people, and the formation of a personal ('I') concept.[2].

By communicating with people around them, developing speech, interacting with peers and adults, the child acquires new knowledge through self-awareness and observation.

Social competency is a set of skills that provide children with the tools and abilities to successfully navigate the world around them. *Developing Social Competency in Young Children* looks at each of the seven Cs of social

competence—communication, community building, coping, confidence, conflict resolution, control, and curiosity.

During any given day, a child will enter and exit many group situations. More often than not, children lack the knowledge and experience to be socially competent in all situations. There is not a switch or a specific age when children automatically become socially competent and adults often assume that when children reach a certain age or milestone they will know how to effectively employ the seven Cs of social competency without being taught.

These skills must be taught and environments need to be designed to encourage the development of these skills while intentionally providing opportunities to test and hone them. *Developing Social Competency in Young Children* examines the role of the adult in designing the environment and using intentional strategies to maximize a child's success. At the end of each skill discussed, there are parent and staff educational tips and strategies that can be used in everyday life.

The child's competencies also determine the areas of development (preschool children aged 6-7 years).

- Physical development and the formation of a healthy lifestyle
- Socio-emotional development
- Speech, communication, reading and writing skills
- Development of the cognitive process
- Creative development

Physical development and the formation of a healthy lifestyle: the child performs physical activities related to his capabilities and age, develops fine motor skills by organizing games using various objects, acquires personal hygiene and nutrition standards.

Social and emotional development: the concept of self develops, manages his emotions, can communicate with peers, easily communicates with adults and friends.

Speech, communication, reading and writing skills: can pronounce words correctly, compose various sentences, learn new words, acquires initial knowledge of a foreign language, is interested in fiction, speaks after listening to fairy tales, expresses his emotions.

Development of the cognitive process: a child aged 6-7 knows how to count numbers, performs elementary mathematical calculations, expresses his attitude, is interested in gaining knowledge.

Creative development: can describe an object based on its shape, participates in finger theater with the help of adults, can recite musical notes, and sing along to songs. In conclusion, it is necessary to develop not only the child's competence, but also the educator, working on himself, increasing creativity, using new modern technologies and methods to help improve the quality of education, and developing professional competence.

References:

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